

Is Talent Management the new Human Resource Management?

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ABSTRACT

Objectives: This is a descriptive cross-sectional study done in Pune, to understand the Human Resource department's credence on the concept of Talent Management (TM) as a new tool for Human Resource Management (HRM) and the problems associated with Talent Management.

Materials and Methods: Descriptive hypotheses were set and studied based on primary data collected from 100 HR managers from Pune. Agreement/disagreement levels of the respondents were obtained for the two questions: a. Is TM the new HRM? b. What are the problems with TM? 10 items under each of the variables were put up by way of a questionnaire. Sample means were compared against the hypothesized population means of 50% agreement/disagreement and were tested for statistical significance at 95% confidence level.

Results: 80% disagreement was found while accepting TM as the new HRM for the arguments in favor of the concept. This was matched by an agreement of 78% for the identified problems for TM.

Conclusion: The HR managers have denied that TM is the new HRM. At the same time, they have expressed their wide agreement for the challenges identified for TM.

Keywords: Human Resource Management (HRM), Talent Management (TM), HR Managers

INTRODUCTION

Talent is an amalgamation of ability, motivation, and opportunity. It is an imperative asset of the human resource that translates into better productivity for the organization. *Managing the talent*, this term is now coined as *Talent Management*, is a strategic cohesive approach by human resource management (HRM) to attract, develop, and retain their truly talented people. The hallmark of all good organizations is to give importance to talent management starting at the recruitment stage and nurture the bests at all levels (Van Dijk, 2008).

Human resource management's business is to *recruit, maintain and develop talent* i.e. is to familiarize the employees of the organization with its goals and objectives and ensure that the strategies of the organization are being implemented for better profit (Van Dijk, 2008). But the best-talented employees tend to gravitate towards greener pastures with better pay and working environment and therefore trying to retain talented people (read- Talent Management) in the company has become a mainstay for the human resource department. The human resource department is now aware that employees are the most important ingredient to the recipe of profit and productivity of the organization and therefore emphasis on talent management as a tool for HRM is inimitable.

So the question arises why is it so difficult for global companies worldwide to attract and retain talent? What are the reasons for the failure of Talent Management in global companies? Therefore this research study conducted in Pune, India wants to explore the concept of Talent Management as a new HRM tool and the significant problems associated with the same.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The term Talent Management is getting in the right person at the right time for any given job, which involves workforce and succession planning along with the development of the employee and their career management (Cappelli & Keller, 2014).

Gallardo et al., (2013) has put forth the theory of an inclusive and exclusive approach to talent management. In the older inclusive approach, all employees were given equal weights as to adding value to the organization and were given equal healthcare and retirement benefits and in the recent HRM favorable exclusive approach model suggests that only a subset of employees or jobs are given higher values as resources of the company are scarce and this hierarchical treatment will yield greater returns to the company. Another aspect of the talent management element is to identify the requirements of the strategic job in the company and assess and develop the abilities of the concerned individuals.

As early as 1920 General Electric (GE) was one of the first companies that implemented the notion that talent should be internally developed and nurtured. By the 1950s tools of internal management used were: refined recruitment and selection techniques; assessing potential candidates using personality tests; development duties like job rotation, shadowing, mentoring, 360-degree feedback, ranking, career ladders- were features of modern talent management practices in those days. But after 2000, only 1% agrees with this theory of internal management rules and presently extensive external hiring for mid and upper-level job positions has escalated to over 60% (Cappelli & Keller, 2014).

The issue of retention of talent has been caused by the employers themselves as they have not been very reassuring to the employees of continued employment which has driven the employees, especially the high profile ones (55%), to take the matter into their own hands and now keeping an eye on external opportunities as and when they arise and leave, this happens almost every 3-4 years among the executives (Bidwell and Keller, 2013).

Another study by Collings and Mellahi (2009), have defined strategic talent management as a series of systematic activities and process to identify key positions of the company's sustainable competitive advantage and to develop a talent pool of high performing individuals to fill these positions and ensure their retention and continuing obligation to the organization.

A study by Günter et al., (2012), has elaborated that internal fit; cultural fit, and strategic fit are major drivers of outstanding talent management that contribute to organizational learning and knowledge management. Talent management in an organization should have other stakeholders other than HR for example CEO and managers of other divisions. Collings and Mellahi's (2009) research study has shown that a survey done in the UK showed that 20%-50% of the CEOs do spend their time looking into the talent issues.

Günter et al., (2012), has given an example of Infosys, the Indian IT giant, which has incorporated principles of emphasizing on core values and principles of the company. To understand their recruits better and differentiate itself from its contenders, they have allowed its knowledge workers to express professional freedom, openness, and exceptional growth and learning opportunities

Leadership development is also the new talent management agenda by leading companies like IBM by either developing learning centers on the campus or tying up with good universities for educational services. Leadership training is meant to *promote from within policy* to retain talent Günter et al., (2012).

As a final point, along with financial incentives, a good corporate culture, learning and growth opportunities, a stirring purpose, work-life balance i.e. flexible working arrangements, especially to women employees are some of the rudiments to try and retain talent in the organizations Günter et al., (2012).

METHODOLOGY

1. A survey questionnaire was administered to 100 HR Managers from MNCs from Pune.
2. The selection of the 100 HR Managers was based on the judgment of the writer of getting an adequate response in a reasonable time. Judgmental sampling was used.
3. The survey questionnaire was divided into two parts:
Part A: Is TM the new HRM?
Part B: Problems with TM
4. 10 questions each for the two sections were framed and responses were sought on Likert-scales.
5. Responses were obtained on a scale of 0-4: 0-Can't say, 1-Somewhat agree, 2-Strongly agree, 3-Somewhat disagree, 4-Strongly disagree
6. To distinguish the somewhat responses from the strong responses, a weight of 2 was assigned to each of the strong responses while doing the analysis.
7. T-test was used at 95% confidence level and the sample mean (higher of agreement or disagreement) was tested for statistical significance by comparing it with a hypothesized population mean taken at 50% agreement or disagreement connoting an event by chance

Statement of Hypotheses:

H_{o1}: TM is the new HRM

H_{a1}: TM is not the new HRM

H_{o2}: There are no significant problems for TM

H_{a2}: There are significant problems for TM

Following ten reasoning (based on a literature review) were given to support the claim that TM is the new HRM:

Table 1: Why TM is the new HRM?

Sr. No.	TM as the new HRM
1	A clear long-term perspective
2	A strategic intent
3	Goes well beyond and addresses issues like leadership crisis
4	Coping up with the turbulent business environment
5	Ensures meaningful engagement of employees
6	Covers the entire gamut of activities right from talent acquisition to succession planning
7	Highly comprehensive in nature
8	Views human resource as human capital
9	Highly popular in the West
10	A robust framework for best utilization of talent

The ten items of significant problems of Talent management as sourced from literature (Mellahi, K. and Collings, D.G. (2010)

Table 2: Problems for TM

Sr. No.	Problems for TM
1	Lack of talent from within the company to fill strategic positions to develop the business
2	Inability to align talent management strategies to business strategies
3	The apparent inability of senior managers to dedicate time to talent concerns
4	Increased stress on individual performance
5	Mismatches between demand and supply
6	Hiring too many employees leading to layoffs and restructuring
7	Too little talent leading to talent shortages
8	Lack of operational definition of talent management in an organization
9	Lack of competent human resources
10	Companies engaging in internal competition regarding the transfer of best talent within the company

The survey instrument returned a Cronbach's alpha of 0.8655 that is better than 0.70 (the standard) and hence was considered as reliable.

RESULTS

The sample constituted a slightly higher number of males (51) as compared to the female faculty (49). Most of them belonged to the age group of 40-50 years (38) and had 15-20 years of experience (54). Most of the respondents were of the designation of Managers (42).

Inferential analysis:

The null hypotheses were set as the sample mean (\bar{x}) equals the hypothesized population mean (μ). Summary of the responses to the two sections is given in Table 3 and Table 4 below:

Table 3: Disagreement responses for the question is TM the new HRM

Sub-questions	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	Total
Average disagreement %	82%	80%	77%	81%	83%	78%	78%	78%	84%	79%	80%

Table 4: Summary of responses for significant problems for Talent management

Problems	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	Total
Average agreement %	86%	86%	76%	72%	80%	64%	90%	75%	66%	86%	78%

Table 5 shows the testing of the two hypotheses at a 95% confidence level.

Table 5: Testing of the hypotheses

Parameter	H ₁ value	H ₂ value
Sample Mean (\bar{x})	80%	78%
Hypothesized population mean (μ)	50%	50%
SD of sample	0.89867	0.91141
n (sample size)	100	100
t-value= $\text{abs}((\bar{x} - \mu) / (s/\sqrt{n}))$	3.33104	3.44912
p-value = $\text{tdist}(t,(n-1),1)$	0.00061	0.00038
Decision	Reject Null	Reject Null

Both the null hypotheses were rejected in favor of the alternate that the sample means are significantly different from the hypothesized population mean of 50% agreement or disagreement.

DISCUSSION OF RESULT

The average disagreement to the 10 arguments in favor of the claim that TM is the new HRM was 80%. The propositions put forward in justification of the claim like A clear long-term perspective, A strategic intent, Goes well beyond and addresses issues like leadership crisis, Coping up with the turbulent business environment, Ensures meaningful engagement of employees, Covers the entire gamut of activities right from talent acquisition to succession planning, Highly comprehensive in nature, Views human resource as human capital, Highly popular in the West and Robust framework for best utilization of talent were widely disagreed by the HR managers. The average agreement to the 10 problems identified for TM was 78%. The identified problems like Lack of talent from within the company to fill strategic positions to develop the business, Inability to align talent management strategies to business strategies, Apparent inability of senior managers to dedicate time to talent concerns, Increased stress on individual performance, Mismatches between demand and supply, Hiring too many employees leading to layoffs and restructuring, Too little talent leading to talent shortages, Lack of operational definition of talent management in an organization, Lack of competent human resources and Companies engaging in internal completion regarding the transfer of best talent within the company were widely agreed by the HR Managers.

CONCLUSION

The HR managers have clearly denied that TM is the new HRM. There is a strong disagreement for TM entirely replacing HRM. This shows the loyalty of the HR managers to the original concepts and reluctance to accept the new ones as complete substitutes for them. Old is gold, is what they want to convey. This disagreement draws support from the literature. Paul Iles (2010), in his research article “Talent management as a management fashion in HRD: Towards a research agenda”, considered whether Talent Management (TM), as a recently-emerged area of interest for HRD, can be argued to display features of a management fashion. Based on a review of three main perspectives, the author concluded that it was too early to say about two of them, given TM’s recent emergence and the paucity of empirical material, but that TM displays features of institutionalism in TM talk in the business and professional literature. At the same time, they have expressed their wide agreement for the challenges identified for TM.

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